

BLAST RESISTANT AIRLINE BAGGAGE CONTAINER DESIGN

D. Erich Weerth

*Chief Technology Officer
Friedman Research Corporation
111 La Patera Lane, Goleta, California 93117, USA*

SUMMARY: A novel patent pending baggage container design solution is presented for the protection of wide body commercial aircraft from the shock, overpressure, fire and fragmentation projectile threats generated by the detonation of an Improvised Explosive Device (IED) planted in baggage stowed in containers used on such aircraft. This blast resistant baggage container design offers passenger and aircraft survivability at the same acquisition plus operating cost as an unhardened conventional aluminium container, commonly referred to as a Unit Load Device (ULD-3) and weighs 91 kg (200 lb). This represents a weight increase of only 7 percent relative to an unhardened aluminium ULD-3.

KEYWORDS: Improvised Explosive Device, Blast Mitigation, Vacuum Infusion Processing

Fig. 1 Crash of Pan Am 103 by an Improvised Explosive Device planted in stowed luggage

INTRODUCTION

On December 21, 1988, Pan Am flight 103 exploded over Lockerbie, Scotland, killing 270 people. This air disaster of the century resulted from the detonation of an IED planted within luggage stored in the aircraft cargo hold. Detonation of the IED caused a breach in the aircraft fuselage and subsequent crack propagation along a circumferential row of rivets just aft of the cockpit. As a result, the nose of the plane severed from the aircraft (Figure 1). Such events can be avoided by a combination of explosives detection and baggage container hardening. However, quantities of explosive which fall below the equipment detection threshold could still find their way into an aircraft's cargo hold. Detonation of such a quantity of explosives is mitigated by the Hardened Unit Load Device (HULD) described herein.

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Friedman Research Corporation (FRC) has developed an extremely lightweight blast resistant baggage container for wide body aircraft that provides enhanced aircraft survivability from the threat of an IED detonation in stowed luggage. The blast resistant container provides a protective boundary between the aircraft fuselage and the suitcase containing the IED. The aircraft fuselage is protected from the IED detonation without catastrophic structural airframe failure or failure to critical electrical and/or hydraulic subsystems.

Fig. 2: ULD-3 Type baggage containers stowed in the cargo hold of a Boeing 747.

Illustrated in Fig. 2 is a typical wide body aircraft cargo hold configuration utilizing side-by-side ULD-3 containers [1]. The ULD-3 type container [2] is the most common baggage container utilized by wide bodied aircraft worldwide and is therefore the configuration upon which this paper will focus. A typical ULD-3 is made of aluminium and weighs 85 kg (187 lb.) with a loaded maximum gross weight of 1588 kg (3494 lb.). The outside dimensions of a conventional aluminium ULD-3 container are 162.5 cm (64 in.) high by 200.7 cm (79 in.) wide by 153.4 cm (60.4 in.) long (deep). The inside dimensions of a conventional aluminium ULD-3 container are illustrated in Fig. 3 and enclose a volume of 4.2 cu. m.(147 cu. ft.).

Fig. 3: The inside dimensions of a typical aluminium ULD-3 type baggage container

FRC BLAST RESISTANT CONTAINER DESIGN

This paper describes a unique patent pending blast resistant, aircraft baggage, container design as well as the methodology behind this novel baggage container approach. In order to be an attractive solution for the airline industry, a hardened, blast resistant, baggage container must be cost competitive compared to a current unhardened, aluminium container. Such cost competitiveness must exist at both the acquisition and operating cost levels. Consequently, a hardened, blast resistant, baggage container (i.e. HULD) must weigh as much as, and cost no more than an unhardened, conventional, aluminium ULD-3, otherwise the HULD will not be accepted by the airline industry. Such stringent design conditions pose an exceptional challenge. As will be described in this paper, the FRC HULD design has met this challenge, offering an extremely attractive solution to this problem in three important areas:

- **Maximum Blast Capacity** – The FRC HULD design exhibits an explosive blast mass efficiency exceeding that of any HULD-3 container available in today’s marketplace;
- **Minimum Weight** – The FRC design represents the lightest HULD-3 container weight available and contains explosive gases within desirable venting levels without rupture while weighing almost the same as today’s unhardened aluminium container;
- **Affordable Cost** – The FRC design represents a much more economical solution than any other container, hardened or unhardened, particularly when considering reduced operating life cycle costs by virtue of its highly damage tolerant and robust design.

Fig. 4: Blast Resistance Curves Comparing Various Metal & Composite Material Systems

The pedigree of FRC's solution is historically based on private research and development activities directly related to the application of fibre reinforced, polymer matrix, composite materials to the construction of military land combat vehicle hull structures designed to defeat projectiles and land mine threats. The FRC HULD solution combines a novel design and manufacturing process together with a proprietary fibre reinforced, polymer matrix, composite material system.

The blast capacity of the design is enhanced by the nature of the advanced composite materials used in conjunction with a totally unique vacuum infusion manufacturing process. The reinforcing fibre employed in the FRC HULD design utilizes a special coating on the S-2®Glass fibre (or Kevlar fibre) which promotes excellent structural blast resistance while simultaneously providing superior ballistic performance in the defeat of fragmentation threats. Fig. 4 illustrates the comparison of four different material systems with respect to explosive blast resistance based on 0% probability of panel rupture. The blast resistance of the FRC HULD material system, designated FRC² (Friedman Research Corporation Fibre Reinforced Composite) is compared to that of graphite/epoxy, titanium and aluminium. Evident in Fig. 4 is the weight efficiency of the FRC² material system in resisting panel rupture resulting from explosive detonation, compared to the other material systems depicted.

Fig. 5: Three Nested Shells Comprise the FRC Blast Resistant Container Design

The FRC HULD design reacts the blast overpressure without rupture by making the HULD “think” it is a spherical container (i.e. pressure vessel), where each of three nested shells, shown in Fig. 5, react the overpressure by developing circumferential “hoop” stresses about three orthogonal axes X, Y and Z. The Inner Shell, designated (I), reacts circumferential stresses about the X axis, whereas the Middle Shell, designated (M), reacts circumferential stresses about the Y axis and the External Shell, designated (E), reacts circumferential stresses about the Z axis. When all three shells are nested together (i.e. I inside M and E surrounding the nested I/M assembly) a rectangular box is then made to behave like a spherical shell. In a thin walled spherical shell, the membrane stress everywhere on the surface of the shell is given by $\sigma = pR/2t$ (where p is the internal pressure; R is the radius of the sphere and t is the wall thickness of the spherical shell). Such “outside the box” way of thinking represents the *best utilization of material* by uniformly stressing all of the material in the fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite used in constructing the container. This results in a *truly minimum weight design* since none of the material is under-utilized.

Fig. 6 illustrates the derivation of the equations of equilibrium for each nested shell when the entire nested assembly is subjected to an internal overpressure, p. It should be noted that the nesting of all three (3) shells creates a condition where each container side consists of two (2) nested shell wall thicknesses. For simplicity the equations derived in Fig. 6 assume an equal sided box where $H = W = L$ (i.e. a cube). Consequently, in this simplified geometry it can be seen that the cube develops membrane stresses in each nested wall on the order of $\sigma = pL/4t$. This is similar in form to the membrane stress developed in a spherical shell where $\sigma = pD/4t$. The characteristic dimension for the sphere is the diameter, D, whereas, the characteristic dimension for each of the nested shells comprising the box is L.

A novel manufacturing process also contributes to increased blast capacity. Each of the three parts comprising the HULD is manufactured by the winding of woven broadgoods and curing via Vacuum Infusion Processing (VIP). The Inner Shell (I) is formed by winding fabric around a collapsible mandrel, then vacuum bagging and resin infusing the preform. Once cured, the (I) Shell is wrapped with a non-stick film and then used as the tool for the Middle Shell (M). The (M) Shell preform is subsequently vacuum bagged, resin infused, cured and wrapped with another layer of non-stick film. Finally the External Shell (E) is then formed by winding fabric around the cured (I/M) assembly. The (E) Shell preform is bagged, infused and cured. After subsequent heat treatment, the container door opening is cut out and the interior collapsible mandrel is removed. The assembly then undergoes trimming, installation of the folding accordion door and final assembly onto the base plate.

The end result is a cost effective, minimum weight HULD which is fully compatible with standard aircraft cargo loading systems [2] [3] [4] currently in service worldwide. Most importantly, the unit does not rupture and therefore requires no undesirable venting of the detonation, thereby further reducing any threat to aircraft survivability. The FRC HULD is extremely durable, and resistant to harsh chemical agents and solvents. It is also resistant to impact, water intrusion, galvanic corrosion and ultra-violet degradation and satisfies all applicable United States Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) flammability and toxicity requirements [5].

Fig. 6: Nested Container Shell Equations of Equilibrium

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